

EXPERIENCE OF INTERACTION OF A COMBINED ARMS UNIT WITH OTHER FORCES IN THE DEFENSE OF POPULATED AREAS IN MODERN ARMED CONFLICTS

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ANNOTATION: The article examines the experience of interaction between combined arms units and other forces in the defense of populated areas in modern armed conflicts. Particular attention is paid to examples from the Russian-Ukrainian armed conflict. Various aspects of interaction are analyzed, such as coordination of actions, joint planning and exchange of intelligence information.

KEY WORDS: Interaction of forces, defense of populated areas, Russian-Ukrainian conflict, coordination of actions, joint planning.

The defense of populated areas is one of the key tasks of armed forces in modern conflicts. At the same time, to effectively accomplish this task, effective interaction between various types of armed forces and special units is necessary. The interaction of forces allows for more efficient use of available resources, increased firepower and increased defense stability.

The article will examine the experience of interaction between combined arms units and other forces in the defense of populated areas in modern armed conflicts. Particular attention will be paid to examples from the Russian-Ukrainian armed conflict.

Coordination of actions. One of the key aspects of interaction between forces is coordination of actions. For effective coordination, it is necessary to establish communication between departments, determine common goals and objectives, and develop a unified action plan.

An example of effective coordination of actions between units is the defense of Debaltseve during the armed conflict in eastern Ukraine. During the battles for this settlement, Ukrainian forces were able to establish effective cooperation between various types of armed forces and special units. Thanks to this, they managed to hold the settlement for several months, despite the enemy's significant superiority in manpower and equipment.

The use of tank troops in populated areas is one of the most complex and challenging tasks for military commanders and tank crews. In modern armed conflicts, the fighting often takes place in urban areas, where the dense buildings, narrow streets, and civilian population create a unique and difficult environment for the use of tanks. In populated areas, communication and coordination between tank crews and other military units can be difficult. The dense buildings and narrow streets can interfere with radio communications, and the presence of a large number of civilians can create noise and confusion. In addition, the complexity of the situation in populated areas requires constant coordination and adjustment of plans, which can be difficult to achieve in practice.

Joint planning. Joint planning of combat operations for the defense of populated areas is an important element of interaction of forces in modern armed conflicts. Effective joint planning allows for more efficient use of available resources, increased firepower and increased defensive resilience. Some of the key aspects of joint combat planning are coordination, intelligence sharing and the use of modern technology. Examples of effective joint planning of military operations for the defense of populated areas include the battles for Mariupol, Lugansk airport

and Avdiivka during the armed conflict in eastern Ukraine. In general, the experience of joint planning of combat operations for the defense of populated areas during the Russian-Ukrainian armed conflict shows that in order to effectively carry out this task it is necessary to establish effective interaction between various types of armed forces and special units, as well as to use modern technologies.

Modern technologies can greatly facilitate the process of joint combat planning. For example, with the help of automated troop control systems, you can effectively coordinate the actions of units, as well as quickly respond to changes in the situation. An example of the use of modern technologies in joint planning of military operations is the defense of Avdiivka during the armed conflict in eastern Ukraine. During the battles for this populated area, Ukrainian forces actively used automated command and control systems, which allowed them to effectively coordinate the actions of units and quickly respond to changes in the situation.

Exchange of intelligence information. Exchange of intelligence information is an important element of force interaction. Thanks to the exchange of information, units can plan their actions more effectively, as well as respond in a timely manner to changes in the situation. An example of effective exchange of intelligence information is the defense of Lugansk airport during the armed conflict in eastern Ukraine. During the battles for this object, Ukrainian forces were able to establish effective cooperation between various types of armed forces and special units. Thanks to the exchange of intelligence information, they managed to hold the objective for several months, despite the enemy's significant superiority in manpower and equipment. During the armed conflict in eastern Ukraine, during the defense of Luhansk airport, Ukrainian troops exchanged and delivered intelligence information using several communication channels and various forces.

One of the main communication channels for the exchange of intelligence information was radio stations. Ukrainian troops used both fixed and portable radios

for communication between units and headquarters. In addition, to ensure the security of information transfer, Ukrainian troops used encryption devices.

Ukrainian troops also used couriers to deliver intelligence information. These were specially trained military personnel who delivered information from the combat zone to headquarters, and also transmitted orders and instructions from headquarters to units.

In addition, Ukrainian troops used unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to collect and deliver intelligence information. The UAVs could fly over enemy positions and transmit images and video in real time. This allowed Ukrainian troops to respond timely to changes in the situation and effectively plan their actions. In general, to ensure the effective exchange and delivery of intelligence information in the defense of Luhansk airport, Ukrainian troops used multiple communication channels and a variety of forces, including radios, couriers and UAVs. This allowed them to respond timely to changes in the situation and effectively plan their actions.

The interaction of armies is one of the key factors determining success in modern armed conflicts. For effective interaction it is necessary to establish communication between departments, coordinate actions, promptly respond to changes in the situation and effectively use available resources.

In this context, unmanned aerial vehicles (drones) are playing an increasingly important role. Drones can perform various tasks, such as reconnaissance, target designation, fire adjustment and cargo delivery, which can improve the interaction of armies and increase the effectiveness of combat operations.

One of the main tasks of drones in modern armed conflicts is reconnaissance. Drones can fly over enemy positions and transmit images and video in real time.

This allows you to respond to changes in the situation in a timely manner and effectively plan your actions.

In addition, drones can be equipped with specialized sensors such as radar, thermal imaging and chemical sensors, which allows them to perform various types of reconnaissance such as radar, electronic signals, optical and chemical.

Drones can also be used for targeting. They can detect targets and transmit their coordinates to artillery, aviation or other units. This allows you to increase the accuracy and efficiency of fire, as well as reduce the time for preparing and conducting combat operations.

Drones are playing an increasingly important role in organizing the interaction of armies in modern armed conflicts. They can perform various tasks, such as reconnaissance, target designation, fire adjustment and cargo delivery, which improves the interaction of armies and increases the effectiveness of combat operations.

It can be said as a conclusion, the interaction of forces is an important element of the defense of populated areas in modern armed conflicts. Effective cooperation allows for more efficient use of available resources, increased firepower and increased defense stability.

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